

Avula A, Acharya S, Anwar S, Narula N, Chalhoub M, Maroun R, Thapa S, Friedman Y. Indwelling Pleural Catheter (IPC) for the Management of Hepatic Hydrothorax: The Known and the Unknown. J Bronchology Interv Pulmonol. 2021 Nov 10. doi: 10.1097/LBR.0000000000000823. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 34753862.

Appendix

Search strategies

Database/Interface: MEDLINE/PubMed			
Date of Search: December 1, 2020			
Limits: English language			
Search number	Terms	Query	Results
1	Hepatic hydrothorax	(hepatic hydrothorax) OR (hepatic hydropneumothorax)	494
2	Hydrothorax + cirrhosis Pleural effusion + cirrhosis	("hydrothorax"[MeSH Terms] OR (hydrothorax) OR "pleural effusion"[MeSH Terms] OR (pleural effusion) OR (intrathoracic fluid)) AND ("liver cirrhosis"[MeSH Terms] OR (cirrhosis))	1,610
3		#1 OR #2	1,777
4	Indwelling pleural catheter	(Indwelling pleural catheter)	568
5	Pleurx catheter	Pleurx	55
6	Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	"portasystemic shunt, transjugular intrahepatic"[MeSH Terms] OR ((transjugular intrahepatic) AND (shunt OR stent))	4,111
7	Thoracentesis	"thoracentesis"[MeSH Terms] OR thoracentesis OR ((pleura OR pleural) AND (aspiration OR puncture OR punction)) OR pleuracentesis OR pleurocentesis OR thoracocentesis	7,013
8		#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7	11,538
9		#3 AND #8	349
10	Limits: Language	#9 AND (English[Language])	308

Database/Interface: Embase/Elsevier (Embase & MEDLINE)			
Date of Search: December 1, 2020			
Limits: English language			
Search number	Terms	Query	Results

1	Hepatic hydrothorax	'hepatic hydrothorax'/exp OR 'hepatic hydrothorax'	712
2	Hydrothorax	'hydrothorax'/exp OR 'hydrothorax' OR 'hydropneumothorax' OR 'intrathoracic fluid'	5,108
3	Pleural effusion	'pleura effusion'/exp OR 'effusion, pleura' OR 'pleura effusion' OR 'pleural effusion' OR 'pleurorrhea' OR 'pleurorrhoea'	68,868
4	Cirrhosis	'liver cirrhosis'/exp OR 'cirrhosis' OR 'cirrhosis hepatic' OR 'cirrhosis, liver' OR 'cryptogenic liver cirrhosis' OR 'dietary cirrhosis' OR 'dietary liver cirrhosis' OR 'hepatic cirrhosis' OR 'liver cirrhosis' OR 'postnecrotic liver cirrhosis'	204,554
5		(#2 OR #3) AND #4	2,282
6		#1 OR #5	2,330
7	Indwelling pleural catheter	'indwelling pleural catheter'/exp OR 'indwelling pleural catheter' OR (indwelling AND pleural AND ('catheter'/exp OR catheter))	838
8	Pleurx catheter	Pleurx	228
9	Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	'transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt'/exp OR 'tips (transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt)' OR 'portasystemic shunt, transjugular intrahepatic' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portasystemic shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porta-systemic shunting' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porta-systemic shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portacaval shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portacaval shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portal systemic shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portal systemic shunting' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portal systemic shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portasystemic shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portasystemic shunting' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portasystemic shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portasystemic stent' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portasystemic stents' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porto-systemic shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porto-systemic shunting' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porto-systemic shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porto-systemic stent' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porto-systemic stent-shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic porto-systemic stents' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portocaval shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portocaval shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunting' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic stent' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic stent-shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic stents' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic shunt' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic shunts' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic stent' OR 'transjugular intrahepatic stents'	6,201

10	Thoracentesis	'thoracocentesis'/exp OR 'aspiration, pleura' OR 'pleura aspiration' OR 'pleura punction' OR 'pleura puncture' OR 'pleuracentesis' OR 'pleural aspiration' OR 'pleural punction' OR 'pleural puncture' OR 'pleurocantensis' OR 'pleurocentesis' OR 'thoracentesis' OR 'thoracocentesis'	10,482
11		#7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10	17,234
12		#6 AND #11	757
13	Limits: Language	#12 AND [english]/lim	710

Duplicates (PubMed): 240

Original citations: 470

Database/Interface: Web of Science/Clarivate (Science Citation Index Expanded 1991-present)			
Date of Search: December 1, 2020			
Limits: English language			
Search number	Terms	Query	Results
1	Hepatic hydrothorax	TS=((hepatic hydrothorax) OR (hepatic hydropneumothorax))	525
2	Hydrothorax + cirrhosis Pleural effusion + cirrhosis	TS=((hydrothorax OR (pleural effusion*) OR (intrathoracic fluid)) AND cirrhosis)	511
3		#1 OR #2	790
4	Indwelling pleural catheter	TS=(Indwelling pleural catheter)	415
5	Pleurx catheter	TS=(Pleurx)	74
6	Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	TS=((transjugular intrahepatic) AND (shunt OR stent))	3,464
7	Thoracentesis	TS=(thoracentesis OR ((pleura*) AND (aspiration OR punct*)) OR pleuracentesis OR pleurocentesis OR thoracocentesis)	3,665
8		#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7	7,506
9		#3 AND #8	248
10	Limits: Language	#9 AND LANGUAGE: (English)	233

Duplicates (PubMed, Embase): 171

Original citations: 62

Database/Interface: Google Scholar Date of Search: December 1, 2020 Limits: English language; publication types (excluded: books, book sections, websites, generic)			
Search number	Terms	Query	Results
1	Hepatic hydrothorax + Indwelling pleural catheter	("indwelling pleural catheter" "indwelling pleural catheters" Pleurx) AND "hepatic hydrothorax"	281
2	Limits: Language; Publication type	Excluded: non-English; books, book sections, websites, generic	198

Duplicates (PubMed, Embase, Web of Science): 59

Original citations: 139

Database/Interface: Scopus/Elsevier Date of Search: December 20, 2020 Limits: English language			
Search number	Terms	Query	Results
1	Hepatic hydrothorax	TITLE-ABS-KEY (hepatic AND (hydrothorax OR hydropneumothorax))	755
2	Hydrothorax + cirrhosis Pleural effusion + cirrhosis	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((hydrothorax OR (pleural PRE/O effusion) OR (intrathoracic PRE/O fluid)) AND cirrhosis)	1,247
3		#1 AND #2	483
4	Indwelling pleural catheter	TITLE-ABS-KEY (indwelling AND pleural AND catheter)	595
5	Pleurx catheter	Pleurx	134
6	Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt	TITLE-ABS-KEY (transjugular PRE/O intrahepatic) AND (shunt OR stent)	5,468
7	Thoracentesis	TITLE-ABS-KEY (thoracentesis OR (pleura* AND (aspiration OR punct*)) OR pleuracentesis OR pleurocentesis OR thoracocentesis)	13,381
8		#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7	19,160

9		#3 AND #8	238
10	Limits: Language	#9 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))	210

Duplicates (PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, Google Scholar): 201

Original citations: 9

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